

A Systematic Study On Phytochemical Screening And Antioxidant Potential Of *Sansevieria Zeylanica* (L.) WILLD With Quantification Of Major Bioactive Constituents

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ABSTRACT

The present research focused on the analysis of phytochemical constituents and antioxidant activity of *Sansevieria zeylanica* leaves using methanolic and aqueous extracts. The extraction process showed that the aqueous extract produced a higher yield (29.69%) compared to the methanolic extract (21.29%), indicating better extraction of polar compounds in water. Preliminary phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of various secondary metabolites including flavonoids, phenols, tannins, glycosides, steroids, and terpenoids in both extracts, whereas alkaloids were predominantly detected in the methanolic extract. This suggests that methanol has a greater capacity to extract a broader range of phytochemicals. Further quantitative analysis demonstrated that the methanolic extract contained higher levels of total flavonoids (6.84±0.206 mg QE/g), total phenols (0.37±0.01 mg GAE/g), and total tannins (13.18±3.89 mg TAE/g) compared to the aqueous extract, which showed lower values (0.24±0.03 mg GAE/g for phenols and 0.82±0.25 mg TAE/g for tannins). These findings indicate that methanol is more efficient in extracting antioxidant-related compounds. The antioxidant potential was assessed using the DPPH radical scavenging method with ascorbic acid as a standard reference. The IC₅₀ values obtained were 921.324 µg/mL for the methanolic extract and 11211.5 µg/mL for the aqueous extract, which are significantly higher than that of ascorbic acid (547.619 µg/mL), indicating weak antioxidant activity. At the highest tested concentration, the methanolic extract showed 42.3±0.95% inhibition, while the aqueous extract exhibited only 5.12±0.67% inhibition.

Keywords: *Sansevieria zeylanica*, phytochemical screening, maceration method, DPPH assay, quantitative analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Sansevieria's are a varied collection of flowering plants that are primarily found in arid environments, while they can also be found in coastal vegetation and tropical forests (Baldwin, 2016). They are indigenous to the Indian subcontinent, Madagascar, Africa, and the Arabian Peninsula (van *et al.*, 2022).

Sansevieria's are common in homes all around the world because they are low-maintenance houseplants with vibrant foliage. "Mother-in-law's tongues," "snake plants," and "bow string hems" are common names associated with sansevierias. Certain species are prized for their ethnobotanical and medicinal uses (Khalumba *et al.*, 2005; Tkachenko *et al.*, 2017).

Studying their development, diversity, ecology, and biogeography as well as evaluating their conservation

status have not advanced due to taxonomic uncertainty in species identification and delimitation, despite their ecological and economic significance, *Sansevieria* were recognized as a separate genus, *Sansevieria* Thunb, until recently (Jankalski, 2008).

The Nolinoideae subfamily of the Asparagales order contains roughly 70 species of *Sansevieria* (Chase *et al.*, 2016). Despite being primarily found in Africa (Carlquist and Schneider, 2007), these plants can be found growing in both tropical and subtropical countries worldwide (Staples and Herbst, 2005). Because *Sansevieria* species can retain a lot of water in their leaves, they can flourish in regions with little rainfall (Widyasanti *et al.*, 2020).

Sansevieria zeylanica is an herbaceous plant that grows to a height of 4 to 5 feet and has tasty, rigid, sunken or wrinkled leaves that are blotched and

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mottled. It is especially common in dry or rocky soil at low elevations. Additionally, it may easily be propagated via seed, suckers, or leaf cuttings, and it can bloom up to 2,000 feet or higher in a damp environment (Rajashekara *et al.*, 2022).

There are 15–20 leaves on the shrub. It is a succulent herb, monocot, perennial plant with a creeping root system and no stem. The plant is made up of spherical, underground rhizomes that are around 12 mm in diameter. The roots are orange and fibrous. There is no petiole. Its fibrous leaves are thick and strapped, with bright and dark green cross bands on the leaf face and darker green parallel lines on the backs. Each of these leaves has a bundle of 400–800 fibrils. The leaves are roughly 400–1000 mm long and 20–30 mm wide, with a concave center. A *S. zeylanica* leaf produces a white fiber that is extremely elastic and durable (Ponnu and Selwin, 2017). Due to the existence of mechanical and ribbon fibers, the morphological, physical, chemical, mechanical, and thermal characteristics of a fiber recovered from the leaves of the *S. zeylanica* plant by the decortication process emerge as a potential support for its composite architectures. The primary cell wall, secondary cell wall, fiber lumen, and middle lamellae make up this fiber (Ponnu and Selwin, 2017).

METHODOLOGY:

1. Collection of plant Materials:

Fresh leaves of plants were collected from the Navrangpura area of the Ahmedabad district. The collected leaves of the plant were washed carefully and dried at a room temperature, ground in the mixer grinder to produce a fine powder. The powdered form obtained after grinding was used for further experiments and analysis.

2. Extract preparation:

The cold extraction methodology, the leaves powder weighed out 10 g by using weighing balance and transferred it into separate flasks. Next, fill each flask with 200 milliliters of methanol, ethanol, and water. The flasks were sealed with parafilm and aluminium foil for 72 hours at room temperature. After the 72 hours of incubation period, the prepared extracts were filtered by using Whatman filter paper. The filtrate was then transferred into petri-dishes for evaporation

at room temperature for 2-3 days. For further process, the petri-dishes are stored in laboratory refrigerator. The percentage yield of extracts was calculated by using the following formula: (Duniya *et al.*, 2018).

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of Dry Extract}}{\text{Weight of Plant Powder Taken}} \times 100$$

3. Phytochemical Screening:

3.1 Qualitative Analysis:

Phytochemical analysis is conducted to identify various active compounds in plants, such as alkaloids, carbohydrates, phenols, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, quinones, and steroids. For preparing the extract, 30 mg of dried plant material is mixed with 30 mL of methanol and Aqueous, creating a stock solution with a concentration of 1 mg/mL (Kenneth *et al.*, 2017).

Test for Alkaloids:

Dragendorff's Test: Take 1ml extract and add few drops of Dragendorff's reagent, resulting in the formation of an orange or reddish-brown precipitate, indicating the presence of alkaloids (Sayma *et al.*, 2025).

Test for Tannins:

Ferric chloride Test: Take 1ml filtrate and add 5% Ferric chloride solution, the formation of dark green or blue or black color indicates the presence of tannins (Ojiuko *et al.*, 2021).

Test for Glycosides:

Keller-Killani test: Take extract and add glacial acetic acid and a drop of ferric chloride, and then concentrated sulfuric acid was added slowly along the side of the test tube, the formation of blue color with a reddish-brown ring indicates the presence of glycosides (Shaikh & Patil, 2020).

Test for Flavonoids:

Lead acetate Test: Take 1ml extract and add few drops of 10% lead acetate solution, the formation of yellow precipitates indicate the presence of flavonoids (Sayma *et al.*, 2025).

Test for Phenols:

Lead acetate Test: Take 1ml extract and add 5ml of distilled water, then add 3ml 10% Lead acetate solution, the formation of white precipitates indicates the presence of phenols (Shaikh & Patil.,2020).

Test for Saponins:

Foam Test: Take 1ml extract and add 3ml distilled water and shake it vigorously, the formation of foam layers indicates the presence of saponins (Dubale *et al.*,2023).

Test for Terpenoids:

Salkowaski's Test: Take 1ml extract and add 2ml chloroform then add 3ml sulfuric acid, the formation of greyish color indicates the presence of terpenoids (Dubale *et al.*,2023).

Test for Proteins:

Millon's test: Take extract and add few drops of Millon's reagent, the formation of white precipitates indicate the presence of protein (Shaikh and Patil.,2020).

Test for Carbohydrates:

Iodin test: Take extract and add 2-3 drops of iodine solution, the formation of blue color indicates the presence of carbohydrates (Pooja *et al.*,2022).

3.2 Quantitative Analysis:

Quantitative analysis of phytochemicals is performed to determine the exact amount of these compounds present in the extracts. To conduct this analysis, a stock solution is prepared with a concentration of 1 mg/mL using methanol as the solvent. This is done by dissolving 10 mg of dry extract in 10 mL of methanol. Likewise, the standard solutions (Quercetin for total flavonoid content) are also prepared with a concentration of 1 mg/mL.

3.2.1 Determination of Total Flavonoids Content:

The colorimetric method was used to measure the total flavonoid content in different extracts. Quercetin, a type of flavonoid, was used as the standard for creating a series of concentrations with slight adjustments. To prepare the standard Quercetin

solution, 10 mg of Quercetin powder is dissolved in 10 mL of methanol, resulting in a concentration of 1 mg/mL. This standard solution is then used to create a concentration series ranging from 50 μ L to 500 μ L. To each sample in the series, 4 mL of water is added, followed by 0.3 mL (300 μ L) of 5% sodium nitrite, then 0.3 mL of 10% aluminium chloride, and finally 2 mL (2000 μ L) of 1M sodium hydroxide. For the plant extract, 1 mL of the extract is mixed with 0.3 mL (300 μ L) of 5% sodium nitrite, followed by 0.3 mL (300 μ L) of 10% aluminium chloride, and then 2 mL (2000 μ L) of 1M sodium hydroxide. The final volume of both the standard and extract solutions is adjusted to 10 mL. The absorbance is measured at 510nm using a UV spectrophotometer. The flavonoid content is then calculated based on a standard curve of Quercetin and is expressed as mg of Quercetin equivalent per gram (QE g-1) using the formula (Kaviya *et al.*,2024).

$$QE = C \times V / M$$

Where, C is the concentration of sample obtained from the equation of standard calibration curve mg/ml,

V is volume of the extract in ml

M is weight of the extract in g

3.2.2 Determination of Total Phenolic Content:

The total phenolic content was measured using the Folin-Ciocalteu method, with gallic acid serving as the standard at different concentrations, formed by a modified series. A standard solution was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of gallic acid powder in 10 mL of water. The concentration series of the standard solution ranged from 10 mg/mL to 50 mg/mL. To each standard, 0.5 mL of 2N Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was added, followed by 10 mL of distilled water. Next, 1 mL of 20% sodium carbonate was added, and the volume was adjusted to 25 mL. The mixture was incubated for 30 minutes, after which the absorbance was measured at 765 nm using a UV spectrophotometer (Siddiqui *et al.*, 2017).

Similarly, for the plant extract, 1 mL of the plant extract in the respective solvent was combined with 0.5 mL of 2N Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, followed by 10 mL of water and 1 mL of 20% sodium carbonate. The volume was then adjusted to 25 mL, and the

mixture was incubated for 30 minutes. After incubation, the absorbance was measured at 765 nm using a UV spectrophotometer. The total phenolic content was quantified as micrograms of gallic acid equivalents per gram of sample. The phenolic content was calculated using the formula:

$$C = C_1 \times V/m$$

Where C = total phenolic content in mg/ml, in GAE (gallic acid equivalent), C₁ = concentration of gallic acid established from the calibration curve in mg/ml, V = Volume of extract in ml, and m = the weight of the plant extract in g (Siddiqui *et al.*, 2017).

3.2.3 Determination of Total Tannin Content:

This phytochemical is produced by the plant as a defense mechanism, offering protection through its strong taste. To determine the total tannin content, the potassium iodate method was employed. Tannic acid was used as the standard, and a concentration series ranging from 100mg/mL to 500mg/mL was prepared. The solution was then placed in a cold water bath for 5 minutes. Afterward, 5 mL of 2.5% potassium iodate (KIO₃) was added, and the mixture was incubated in a test tube for 25 to 30 minutes. The optical density was measured at 550 nm (Willis and Allen.,1998).

For the plant extract, 1 mL of the extract, along with the respective solvent, was used, and the same procedure was followed. The tannin content was calculated from the standard curve of tannic acid and expressed as milligrams of tannic acid equivalent per gram (mg TE/g). The calculation was done using the formula:

$$TE = C \times V/M.$$

3.2.4 Antioxidant activity:

DPPH assay:

This is a widely used method to test the free radical scavenging activity of plant material. 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) is a dark crystalline powder

that contains stable free radical molecules. To prepare the DPPH solution, 4 mg (0.004%) of DPPH is dissolved in 100 mL of methanol. Then, 2 mL of the prepared DPPH solution is mixed with various concentrations of the sample (200, 400, 600, 800, and 1000 µg/mL), and the mixture is incubated in the dark for 30 minutes at room temperature. The absorbance of each concentration is measured at 517 nm in triplicate using a spectrophotometer. DPPH is commonly used in antioxidant assays because it reacts with antioxidants, causing it to lose its color. The more it decolorizes, the stronger the scavenging ability of the sample. Ascorbic acid can be used as a standard in the free radical scavenging test. The antioxidant activity is expressed in terms of mg/g of Ascorbic acid equivalent. The scavenging activity is calculated by determining the percentage of DPPH radicals neutralized, using the following formula:

$$I\% = [(A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}) / A_{\text{control}}] \times 100$$

Where, A_{control} = Absorbance of DPPH solution

A_{sample} = Absorbance of extracts and ascorbic acid solution (Sayma *et al.*,2025).

RESULTS:

1. Percentage yield of the Plant Extract:

The yield (%) of plant extracts shows how much of the plant's chemicals are in the dry extract. The methanolic leaf extract gave a yield of 21.29%, while the aqueous leaf extract gave a yield of 29.69%.

Standard formula Yield (%):

Yield (%) = (Weight of Dry Extract ÷ Weight of Plant Powder Taken) × 100

Calculations:

1. Yield (%) for Methanolic Leaf Extract (2.129 ÷ 10) × 100 = 21.29%
2. Yield (%) for Water Leaf Extract (2.969 ÷ 10) × 100 = 29.69%

Graph 1 : Extract Yield Comparison

2. Qualitative Analysis:

(‘+’ = Presence of Phytochemicals, ‘-’ = Absence of Phytochemicals)

Sr.no	Phytochemicals	Test name	Methanol (leaves)	Water (leaves)
1.	Alkaloids	Dregandroff test	++	-
2.	Tannins	Ferric Chloride test	+	-
3.	Glycoside	K2 test	+	+
4.	Flavanoids	Lead acetate test	++	+
5.	Phenol	Lead acetate test	+	++
6.	Saponin	Foam test	-	++
7.	Terpenoids	Salkowaski’s test	++	++
8.	Protein	Millon’s test	+	+
9.	Carbohydrates (starch)	Iodin test	-	-

Table 1: Qualitative Analysis or Phytochemical Screening

3. Quantitative Analysis:

3.1 Total Flavonoids Content (TFC):

The total flavonoid content present in methanolic Leaf Extract is 6.84±0.206 mg QE/g of the plant extract and in aqueous leaf extract the flavonoid content was negligible.

Concentration (µl)	Absorbance at 510nm
50	0.241±0.004
100	0.365±0.003
200	0.534±0.006
300	0.693±0.008
400	0.839±0.011
500	0.917±0.036

Table 3.2: The Standard reading of Total Flavonoid Content

Graph 2 : Showing the standard curve of flavonoid

Type of Extract	Concentration (µl)	Absorbance
Methanolic Leaf Extract	1000	0.705±0.052
Aqueous Leaf Extract	1000	0.736±0.009

Table 3.3: Total Flavonoid Content absorbance of plant extract

Graph 3 : Total Flavonoid Content (mg QE/g)

3.2 Total Phenol Content (TPC):

The total Phenol content in methanolic leaf extract is 0.37±0.01 mg GAE/g of the plant extract and aqueous extract is 0.24±0.03 mg GAE/g of plant extract.

Concentration (µl)	Absorbance at 765nm
10	0.376±0.003
20	0.539±0.005
30	0.801±0.004
40	1.201±0.007
50	1.415±0.009

Table 3.4: The standard reading of Total Phenol Content

Graph 4 : Showing the standard curve of Phenol

Type of Extract	Concentration (µl)	Absorbance
Methanolic Leaf Extract	1000	0.538±0.009
Aqueous Leaf Extract	1000	0.579±0.035

Table 3.5: Total Phenol Content absorbance of plant extract

Graph 5 : Total Phenol Content (mg GAE/g)

3.3 Total Tannin Content (TTC):

The Total Tannin content in Methanolic leaf extract is 13.18±3.89 mg TAE/g of plant extract and aqueous extract is 0.82±0.25 mg TAE/g of plant extract.

Concentration (µl)	Absorbance at 510nm
100	0.298±0.002
200	0.454±0.003
300	0.596±0.006
400	0.713±0.01
500	0.961±0.024

Table 4.6: The standard reading of Total Tannin Content

Graph 6 : The standard curve of Tannin

Type of Extract	Concentration (µl)	Absorbance
Methanolic Leaf Extract	1000	0.922±0.007
Aqueous Leaf Extract	1000	1.545±0.06

Table 3.7: Total Tannin Content absorbance of plant extract

Graph 7 : Total Tannin Content (mg TAE/g)

3.4 Antioxidant activity

DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay:

The antioxidant activity of the plant was evaluated by DPPH radical scavenging assay. DPPH is a commonly used method for testing antioxidant activity of plant samples. It is a simple and rapid colorimetric method. In this assay, the antioxidant reduces DPPH, which is indicated by a color change from purple to yellow, with a decrease in absorbance at 517 nm measured using a spectrophotometer. To study the antioxidant activity of *Sansevieria zeylanica* leaves, ascorbic acid was used as a standard for comparison. From the results, the standard ascorbic acid showed the highest scavenging activity of 80.47±0.75% at 1000 µg/mL and the lowest 32.42% at 200 µg/mL. The methanolic leaf extract showed moderate activity with 42.3 ± 0.95% inhibition at 1000 µg/mL, while the aqueous extract showed very low activity with only 5.12 ± 0.67% inhibition at the same concentration. The IC₅₀ values were found to be

547.619 µg/mL for ascorbic acid, 921.324 µg/mL for methanolic extract, and 11211.52 µg/mL for aqueous extract.

Sr. no.	Concentration(µl)	Ascorbic acid	Methanol leaf	Aqueous Leaf
1.	200	32.42±0.28	4.3±0.38	1.56±2.76
2.	400	47.44±1.73	11.45±1.76	2.399±0.21
3.	600	58.61±0.48	18.91±0.43	3.421±0.54
4.	800	72.18±0.13	29.09±0.69	4.144±0.23
5.	1000	80.47±0.75	42.3±0.95	5.12±0.67
6.	IC50	547.619 µg/ml	921.324 µg/ml	11211.52 µg/ml

Table 3.8 : The Inhibition of Ascorbic acid and Methanol leaf and Aqueous Leaf

Graph 8 : Methanol and Aqueous extract Inhibition against Standard Inhibition

DISCUSSIONS:

The present study carried out a detailed phytochemical and antioxidant analysis of the leaves of *Sansevieria zeylanica* using methanol and aqueous solvents. The percentage yield obtained showed that aqueous extract (29.69%) was higher than methanolic extract (21.29%), indicating that water extracted more polar compounds from the plant material. However, higher yield did not correspond to higher biological activity. The qualitative phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of important secondary metabolites. The methanolic extract contained alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, glycosides,

steroids, and terpenoids, while the aqueous extract showed flavonoids, phenols, saponins, glycosides, steroids, and terpenoids. These results suggest that methanol is more efficient in extracting a wider range of phytochemicals compared to water, highlighting the importance of solvent polarity in extraction.

The quantitative analysis of bioactive compounds showed clear variation between the extracts. The total flavonoid content (TFC) in methanolic extract was 6.84±0.206 mg QE/g, whereas it was negligible in aqueous extract. The total phenolic content (TPC) was higher in methanol (0.37±0.01 mg GAE/g) compared to aqueous extract (0.24±0.03 mg GAE/g). Similarly,

the total tannin content (TTC) was significantly higher in methanol (13.18±3.89 mg TAE/g) than in aqueous extract (0.82±0.25 mg TAE/g). These results indicate that methanol is a better solvent for extracting phenolics, flavonoids, and tannins from *Sansevieria zeylanica*. The antioxidant activity was evaluated using the DPPH free radical scavenging assay with ascorbic acid as a standard. The IC₅₀ value of ascorbic acid was 547.619 µg/mL, while methanolic extract showed IC₅₀ of 921.324 µg/mL and aqueous extract showed a very high IC₅₀ of 11211.52 µg/mL. Higher IC₅₀ values indicate lower antioxidant activity, which clearly shows that both extracts have weak antioxidant potential. However, the methanolic extract exhibited comparatively better activity than the aqueous extract. The percentage inhibition increased with increasing concentration in both extracts, indicating dose-dependent activity. At higher concentration (1000 µL), methanolic extract showed 42.3±0.95% inhibition, whereas aqueous extract showed only 5.12±0.67% inhibition, which further confirms the poor antioxidant efficiency of aqueous extract. The overall antioxidant activity observed in this study may be due to the combined or synergistic effect of phenolics, flavonoids, and tannins present in the plant. However, despite the presence of these bioactive compounds, their concentration or activity is not sufficient to produce strong antioxidant effects. The general trend observed in this study shows that methanol extract contains higher TFC, TPC, and TTC and also shows better antioxidant activity compared to aqueous extract, although the activity is still weak.

These findings confirm that *Sansevieria zeylanica* contains important phytochemicals but has limited antioxidant potential. Overall, the study supports the traditional medicinal importance of the plant due to its phytochemical composition, but it also clearly indicates that its antioxidant activity is weak and not comparable to standard antioxidants. Therefore, further studies are required to isolate and identify specific active compounds that may enhance its biological activity.

CONCLUSION

The present study confirms that *Sansevieria zeylanica* contains important phytochemicals and shows measurable biological activity. The extraction results indicated that aqueous extract gave a higher yield

(29.69%) compared to methanolic extract (21.29%), suggesting that water extracts more polar compounds. However, higher yield did not result in better antioxidant activity. The qualitative phytochemical screening revealed the presence of various secondary metabolites such as flavonoids, phenols, tannins, glycosides, steroids, and terpenoids. The methanolic extract showed a wider range of phytochemicals compared to the aqueous extract, indicating that methanol is a more effective solvent for extracting bioactive compounds. The quantitative analysis showed that methanolic extract had higher total flavonoid content (6.84±0.206 mg QE/g), total phenolic content (0.37±0.01 mg GAE/g), and total tannin content (13.18±3.89 mg TAE/g) compared to aqueous extract (0.24±0.03 mg GAE/g TPC and 0.82±0.25 mg TAE/g TTC). These results confirm that methanol is more efficient for extracting antioxidant-related compounds. The antioxidant activity evaluated by DPPH assay showed that the plant has weak antioxidant potential. The IC₅₀ values were 921.324 µg/mL for methanol extract and 11211.52 µg/mL for aqueous extract, which are much higher than the standard ascorbic acid (547.619 µg/mL). The methanolic extract showed better activity than aqueous extract, but overall activity remained low. The maximum inhibition observed was 42.3±0.95% for methanol and 5.12±0.67% for aqueous extract, confirming weak free radical scavenging ability. *Sansevieria zeylanica* is rich in phytochemicals but exhibits limited antioxidant activity. The study highlights the importance of solvent selection, as methanol proved to be more effective than water in extracting bioactive compounds. Although the plant has traditional medicinal value, its antioxidant potential is weak, and further research is needed to isolate and enhance its active compounds for better therapeutic applications.

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